

The Antyodaya Philosophy: Government Plan to Rural Development and Rural livelihood security

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ABSTRACT:

Antyodaya Mission is an initiative by the Indian government with a goal to bring optimal utilization and management of resources, convergence and accountability frameworks, and poverty eradication in rural and urban India. The mission is a part of the Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Rural Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NRLM) and the Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana - National Urban Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NULM). It aims to target the poorest and most vulnerable households and transform them into sustainable livelihoods units. Under this mission, the government collects village-level data on infrastructure and economic activities to identify and prioritize the needs of the community. This data is then used to identify and select beneficiaries and provide them with various skill development and income-generating activities.

Implementation of Mission Antyodaya is done through a network of trained resource persons and community facilitators, who work together with communities to develop and implement a local development plan. The mission emphasizes transparency and accountability at all levels of its implementation, including regular monitoring and evaluation by various stakeholders. Overall, the Antyodaya Mission is a significant step towards reducing poverty and promoting sustainable livelihoods in India's rural and urban areas. It highlights the importance of community participation, accountability, and data-driven decision making in achieving this goal. The term "Antyodaya" the concept of Antyodaya as a philosophy and an approach to development was first articulated by Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya, an Indian philosopher, economist and political leader.

KEYWORDS:

Antyodaya Philosophy, Rural Livelihoods, Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya,
Rural, Poverty, Decentralization, India.

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Literally, 'Antyodaya' means the "rise of the last person" A champion, statesman, intellectual and organizer par excellence, Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya has been an alleviation for millions. Antyodaya, the lasting heritage of Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya is the gospel of Integral Humanism, which means " upping up to the last person " or " the rise of the last person ". It's the means to relieve the nation of extreme poverty and to insure a minimum standard of living of all individualities. September 25 every time is now celebrated as Antyodaya Diwas to mark the Birth Anniversary of Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya. He proffered the gospel that in mortal being, the individual and society aren't contending individualities, but indeed the human being himself is the society and the progress of one is the progress of all. This he called " Ekatom Manavtavad " or " Integral Humanism ". Antyodaya is the introductory principle of the political and profitable gospel of Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya. Not forgetting about nature, fulfillment of musts of mortal life including health care for individual, educating individual, work for all and capital conformation were some of the morals defined under the conception of Integral Humanism by Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya. He always believed that the thing of an existent isn't simply to conserve culture, but to give it instigation for its revivification as a dynamic and able reality. His testament proffered that there's a need to develop community leaders who in return can address development issues at the community position. The gospel of Antyodaya, aims at the progress and happiness of " Man ", the " Integral Man ". This means icing that the last person in the graduation or the chain gets the benefit of growth and development. He believed that the profitable schemes and progress can be measured by the person positioned at the smallest position and not at the loftiest position of society and bone

who has risen above the profitable graduation. Unless the weak-

est of humans progresses, the society can not progress! Pandit Deen Dayal Upadhyaya, was one of the founding leaders of Bharatiya Jana Sangh and has been a source of ideologic guidance for the Bharatiya Janata Party since its commencement. In recent times since 2014, " Antodaya " has been one of the guiding principles of the BJP Government at the Centre and the States. Prime Minister, Narendra Modi has said that guided by the ideals and gospel of Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya, we're continuously seeking to ameliorate the quality of life of the crushed. Be it toilets, electricity, bank accounts, gas, education or health care, we've concentrated on furnishing introductory amenities to the poor, underprivileged and depressed sections of society. Mission Antyodaya is a confluence and responsibility frame aiming to bring optimum use and operation of coffers allocated by colorful Ministries and Departments of the Government of India under colorful programmes. It's imaged as a State- led action with Gram Panchayats as focal point of confluence sweats

Background of these schemes

In India, 8.88 crore households are found to be deprived and poor households as per Socio Economic Caste Census (SECC) of 2011 from the perspective of multi-dimensional deprivations such as shelterlessness, landlessness, households headed by single women, SC/ST household or disabled member in the family. These households require targeted interventions under government's various schemes and programmes in areas such as wage creation, skill generation, social security, education, health, nutrition and livelihood creation.

What is mission Antyodaya Literally, 'Antyodaya' means the "rise of the last person" Mission Antyodaya strives to realise the vision of Poverty-free India by 2022-23. Adopted in Union Budget 2017-18, Mission Antyodaya is a convergence and accountability framework aiming to bring optimum use and management of resources allocated by 27 Ministries / Department of the Government of India under various programmes for the development of rural areas. It is envisaged as state-led initiative with Gram Panchayats as focal points of convergence

efforts. Annual survey in Gram Panchayats across the country is an important aspect of Mission Antyodaya framework. It is carried out co-terminous with the People's Plan Campaign (PPC) of Ministry of Panchayat Raj and its' purpose is to lend support to the process of participatory planning for Gram Panchayat Development Plan (GPDP).

The plan Including "Mission Antyodaya Survey" (MAS) 2022-23

The Mission will ensure effective utilization of resources through convergence of various government schemes with a focused micro plan for sustainable livelihood for each marginalized household. Mission Antyodaya Survey 2022-23 Survey will be conducted in all 2,69,253-gram panchayats and equivalent, whose profile has been created on e-Gram Swaraj The Survey-2022 Questionnaire has 183 indicators and 216 data points covering 21 areas and has been translated in 13 regional languages A total of 26 Central Government Ministries / Departments have been consulted for finalization of the questionnaire

Objectives Of Mission Antyodaya

- » Ensuring effective use of resources through the convergence of various Government Schemes with Gram Panchayats as the basic unit of planning.
- » Work with a focused micro plan for sustainable livelihood for every deprived household
- » Conduct an annual survey on measurable outcomes at Gram Panchayat level to monitor the progress in the development process across rural areas
- » Supporting the process of participatory planning for the Gram Panchayat Development Plan (GPDP), which will improve service delivery, enhance citizenship, create a pace for an alliance of people's institutions and groups, and improve governance at the local level.
- » Encourages partnerships with a network of professionals, institutions, and enterprises to further accelerate the transformation of rural livelihoods.

Goals Of Mission Antyodaya

There is a need to bring in synergies between different government programs and schemes in terms of planning, processes, and implementation to achieve the goals of SDG.

- » The Planning should consider the household and the villages as the basic unit of planning that facilitates household-level micro-plan and Gram Panchayat Development Plan (GPDP).
- » Harmonizing selection criteria, implementation processes and guidelines, and availability of funds at the same time is thus critical for implementation. This would need the pooling of financial and human resources in different schemes of government and their rationalization in implementing the plans at the Household level and GPDP.
- » “Mission Antyodaya” encourages addressing all identified deprivations in a time-bound manner through intensifying coverage of government schemes to address individual, household, and community-level deprivations in saturation mode.
- » Provisions of public services and improving access are necessary but not sufficient to address multiple deprivations. In this endeavor, over 25 Departments / Ministries of the Government are expected to provide resources to the Antyodaya GPs / Clusters on a priority basis through their programs with a thrust on pooling of resources and delivery in saturation mode.
- » Mission Antyodaya is an accountability and convergence framework for transforming lives and livelihoods on measurable outcomes.

Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana-National Rural Livelihood Mission (DAY-NRLM) is a scheme launched by the Ministry of Rural Development to alleviate poverty among the rural population in India. While the focus of DAY-NRLM is on rural development, there is a similar mission for urban areas called Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana-National Urban Livelihood Mission (DAY-NULM).

DAY-NULM aims to reduce poverty and vulnerability by enabling the urban poor to access gainful self-employment and skilled wage employment opportunities, leading to an appreciable improvement in their livelihoods on a sustainable basis, through building strong grassroots level institutions of the poor. Therefore, DAY-NULM plays a significant role in improving the livelihoods of the urban poor across India. This is one of the world's largest initiatives to improve the livelihoods of the poor. The Mission seeks to achieve its objective through investing in four core components viz.,

- a. social mobilization and promotion and strengthening of self-managed and financially sustainable community institutions of the rural poor women;
- b. financial inclusion;
- c. sustainable livelihoods;
- d. social inclusion, social development and access to entitlements through convergence.

The Mission seeks to reach out to around 10 Crore rural poor households in a phased manner by 2022-23 and impact their livelihoods significantly.

Deendayal Antyodaya Yojana-National Urban Livelihoods Mission (DAY-NULM): Is To reduce poverty and vulnerability of the urban poor households by enabling them To reduce poverty and vulnerability of the civic poor homes by enabling them to pierce economic tone employment and professed pay envelope employment openings, performing in an perceptible enhancement in their livelihoods on a sustainable base, through erecting strong grassroots position institutions of thepoor.The charge would aim at furnishing harbors equipped with essential services to the civic homeless in a phasedmanner.In addition, the charge would also address livelihood enterprises of the civic road merchandisers by easing access to suitable spaces, institutional credit, social security and chops to the civic road merchandisers for penetrating arising request openings.

Scheme Benefits & Highlights

The scheme encourages the urban poor to start up manufacturing and servicing small enterprises, and petty businesses, based on local skills, crafts, and demand. The following are the 7 components of NULM:

1. Social Mobilization and Institution Development (SM&ID)
2. Employment through Skills Training and Placement(EST&P)
3. Capacity Building and Training (CBT)
4. Self-Employment Programme (SEP)
5. Scheme of Shelter for Urban Homeless (SUH)
6. Support to Urban Street Vendors (SUSV)
7. Innovative and Special project(ISP)

The Financial benefits provided by the scheme are as follow:

1. Self Employment Programme - The urban poor who wish to set up their own self employment ventures/ micro-enterprises can avail bank loan on 7% rate of interest. An individual can be given bank loans for projects upto INR 2 lakh for setting up of individual micro enterprises and for a group of urban poor, bank loan is available for projects up to INR 10 lakh
2. Self Help groups - All the SHGs of urban poor can also avail bank loan on 7% rate of interest. An additional 3 percent interest subvention will be provided to all women SHGs who repay their loan in time. Thus, in case of timely repayment, effective interest rate would be only 4%
3. Urban Street Vendors- NULM aims at skilling of street vendors, support for micro-enterprises development, and their credit enablement

The non-financial benefits provided by the scheme are as follow:

1. Scheme for shelter for Urban Homeless - NULM also provides financial support to State Governments/ULBs for construction as well as

operation & management of permanent shelter for urban homeless. The shelters constructed must be equipped with all other essential services so that the urban homeless in our cities live a dignified life.

2. Urban Street Vendor- It also supports development of vendor market, vending zone & informal sector markets with infrastructure/civic facilities such as paving, water supply, solid waste disposal facility, lighting, storage space etc.

Conclusion

The Indian Constitution mandates local governments to prepare and implement plans for 'economic development and social justice' (Articles 243G and 243W). Several complementary institutions and measures such as the gram sabha to facilitate people's participation, the District Planning Committee (DPC) to prepare bottom-up and spatial development plans, the State Finance Commission (SFC) to ensure vertical and horizontal equity, one-third reservation for women (in most States, now 50%), population-based representation to Scheduled Caste/Scheduled Tribe communities, and so on were introduced to promote this goal. Even so, India's decentralization reforms (with no parallel in federal history) have failed to take the decentralization process forward in delivering social justice and progress in rural India. I argue that given the right momentum, the 'Mission Antyodaya' project of the Government of India launched in 2017-18 (and cast in a convergence framework avowedly to eradicate poverty in its multiple dimensions among rural households) bears great promise to revive the objectives of these great democratic reforms. The Ministry of Panchayati Raj and the Ministry of Rural Development acts as the nodal agents to take the mission forward.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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